

Values Education of Game in 0-6 Age Group Children Investigation of its Effect On

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Abstract

The application of values education studies in Turkey is based on an international study that was initially prepared for the 50th Anniversary celebrations of the United Nations in 1995 under the name of "Living Values Education Program (YDEP)" supported by UNESCO. This study was used as the foundation for the implementation of values education studies in Turkey. Along with other universal values, such as the child's sense of democracy, sense of justice and freedom, as well as the sense of justice and friendship included in the program of the Ministry of National Education, this project has been extensively used in schools, books, puppets, events, children's films, and animations, and finally children's games. Game, which enables youngsters to have fun and to gain pleasure, with the end goal of producing an automatic response to action. For instance, if a youngster loves someone and imitates their conduct during a game, it suggests that the person whose behavior they are modeling is the one who has the most influence on them. It's a game. Simply participating in an activity that gives you joy while simultaneously serving as a trainer is required. your child's life in terms of growth in terms of mental processes

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played games while positively impacting crucial. Additionally, it imparts many talents. Youngsters learn their skills while playing the game; they take ownership of the talents they uncover. The more words a person knows, the more imaginative they become. Enhances your ability to find solutions to problems. Children pick up whole new ideas when playing games, and these lessons are infused with value. They also acquire the education and begin to put it into practice. Children who get an education in values are more likely to mature into adults who have a distinct personality and a congruent morality. When it comes to instilling morals and ethics in a kid, the first and most essential influence is the child's family. After the family comes other factors such as the surroundings and the school. Because even though the kid and the environment are both influenced by the environment in which they live, it is the education that they have gotten that demonstrates how the environment has impacted them while they are at school. As a result, both the setting and the educational institution play a crucial influence. Since we now live in a technological era, the media and social media are on their way. This demonstrates that there is a significant amount of responsibility involved in passing down the norms and beliefs of society to younger generations. As a result of this, it holds a significant position in terms of examining, interpreting, and evaluating the contents that were prepared in accordance with the education and training programs as well as the programs that are implemented in the school in terms of the methods that are utilized on the children. When children are in the pre-school years, between the ages of 0 and 6, which is the age range in which the personality phenomenon develops, they should have the appropriate attitude toward individuals who have diverse traits and cultures. Tolerance is the key to success in this method; hence, the cultivation of healthy persons is essential to the establishment of a harmonious community.

Keywords: *Play, child, values education, preschool education, 0-6 age group, activity, cognitive development, social emotional development, self-care skills, language development, psycho-motor skills.*

1.Introduction

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UNESCO has been a major supporter of this initiative, which has been used in a wide variety of settings, including schools, books, puppets, and events. It is hoped that this would result in the acquisition of fundamental values such as a sense of honesty, a feeling of self-control, a sense of patience, a sense of respect, a sense of love, a sense of responsibility, patriotism, and compassion. Play, which is at the beginning of most of the individual's most frequent acts, gives the kid the opportunity to learn universal values without the child being aware that this is happening. Simply because the kid is a social value whose primary objective is to have a good time. The capability gained in this way is essential for the child to be able to make his own decisions with his own free will and to be able to take responsibility for his decisions without being dependent on anyone else (Dirican and Dal, 2014: 45). This ability is important for the child to be able to make his own decisions with his own free will and to be able to make his own decisions with his own free will. The first indication of a game may be found in the history of cultures via the medium of music. People would move their bodies in time to the beat of the music, have fun, and break all the regulations without even realizing it. Communities of people who were adjusting to the harmony of music would occasionally feel thrilled, dance, have fun, produce new noises, and sometimes sing and sway, and as a result, they would consider themselves as being closer to the one who made them. Archaeological research has unearthed evidence that demonstrates that the history of games and toys dates to the beginning of human civilization. There is evidence in the form of papers and archaeological findings indicating many of the games played now were also played in ancient times.

The game has been around for as long as humans have, making its age older than human history itself. The advancement of civilization in every sector, such as science, art, architecture attire, and children's activities and toys have all mirrored this growth in some way or another. Concepts that take on a human form are called values. The identity of civilizations may be traced back to their core values. Because of this, it is vital to have values in the home, in the school, and in other educational and training institutions, to put them into practice, to keep them alive, and to pass them on to subsequent generations. There are a lot of different ways that value has been defined. Value may be described as a belief in something that is acceptable or undesirable, and a lifestyle can be defined as our behavior patterns that are successful in our everyday routines. Both definitions can be used interchangeably. A very methodical inquiry is being conducted in the subject of values. As a result, another definition for it is as an unchanging

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conviction. It is a circumstance that guarantees the maintenance of the connection that exists between people and the tangible things that already exist. The idea of value may be investigated on a personal level, including a person's requirements, objectives, and aspirations, in addition to societal, cultural, and sociological considerations. The ideas of our lifestyle and the lifestyle that we now lead is often considered associated with the idea of worth. In this sense, experiences, symbols, ideas, and beliefs all come together to form a cohesive whole that can be conceptualized as value. Value may be described as an abstract notion and a reaction to how much something is worth. There is a connection between the presence of values and the influence of family, friends, schools, and religion.

Values are not something that just "happens." The tenacity of people with values is what gives rise to the formation of societies that have solid and good values. An individual's process of socialization is where they get their education in morals and values. Values education cannot be conducted at any given time or location. When is it appropriate to teach children morals and values? There is only one correct response to this inquiry, and that is that the answer must always be provided. Nevertheless, the incorporation of the teachings that are imparted via a good values education beginning in the preschool years has a very significant position in the formation of an individual's personality. Because the kid may learn and teach values education anywhere—in the home, at school—it is important for them to be exposed to these experiences. People can exert more influence on their actions because of their values. The individual is born into an environment that already exists and has been formed, and as the individual grows, he grows according to the elements that are required by the environment and adapts to that environment in a cultural sense. The environment in which the individual is born already exists and has been formed. If he does not make the necessary adjustments, he will be miserable.

The content structures, age levels, social phenomena, and socio-economic situations of children's games all play a role in the manifestation of unique characteristics in these mediums. These characteristics have been used by researchers to categorize various types of games. The categorization of games offers a great deal of convenience for the purposes of study. Piaget (1962) and Smilansky (1968) identified the most chosen game categories in accordance with cognitive domains. Parten (1932) determined the most preferred game classifications in accordance with social facts. Piaget (1962) divided the game into several categories based on different aspects of cognitive development. Exercises in playing the game, - Studies of the

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symbols in the game, - Studies of the rules of the game Piaget, three stages in a row; it outlines the development of games in the first seven years of an individual's life by defining them as practice game work, symbolic play work, and rule play work. Piaget, three stages in a row; it outlines the development of games in the first seven years of an individual's life. These domains are referred regarded as the one-to-one equivalents of the intelligences known as sensory-motor, preoperational, and concrete operational. When children play again, they progress to combinations of movement and manipulation, at first by accident and later purpose. As soon as this occurs, the kid begins to establish objectives and tries to translate practice games into structures. Symbolic Play and Work: In the same way that an individual's building work or action sequences may become symbolic, practice games can also become symbolic. Playwork with Rules: When play work is turned into a group activity in which rules may be established, the activity transforms into "games with rules."

2.Game Development

Game, which enables youngsters to have fun and to gain pleasure, with the end goal of producing an automatic response to action. For instance, if a youngster loves someone and imitates their conduct during a game, it suggests that the person whose behavior they are modeling is the one who has the most influence on them. It's a game. Simply participating in an activity that gives you joy while simultaneously serving as a trainer is required. Your child's life in terms of growth in terms of mental processes played games while positively impacting crucial Additionally, it imparts many talents. Youngsters learn their skills while playing the game; they take ownership of the talents they uncover. The more words a person knows, the more imaginative they become. Enhances your ability to find solutions to problems. Children pick up whole new ideas when playing games, and these lessons are infused with value. They also acquire the education and begin to put it into practice. According to the theory of the preoperational period, an individual is defined by their capacity to create cognitive symbols that stand in for actual objects, to use language appropriately when describing things and happenings, to organize things into categories, and to reason on a fundamental level.

The cognitive development is referred to as "a process that provides interaction with the environment, helps to acquire and use information, helps to perceive the outside world, and

expresses the storage, interpretation, rearrangement, evaluation, and use of information," according to Kandr (2003)'s definition. Memory, self-correction (also known as self-control), verbal speaking, and the ability to recognize symbols are all skills that may be developed via play. The importance of the game lies in the fact that it helps to improve reading skills together with academic talents in other subjects. (Long and Bodrova, 2005:37). Play, intellectual growth, and the expansion of one's horizons are all significant aspects that absolutely must be taken into consideration. - When playing the game, children's capacity to conceive about things in creative new ways is enhanced, and their language development is supported in a constructive manner thanks to the usage of terms like "as if." The game is comprised of two primary aspects. It is the process of developing one's thinking via the continual participation in social interactions. The game serves as the foundation for the student's theoretical understanding. - People are better able to differentiate between meanings and themes because of participating in pretend play, which also contributes to the development of individuals' capabilities to deal with a variety of circumstances. In this manner, he cultivates the talents necessary for better knowing himself. There are several facets of the successful communication event that occur for him to accept propaganda to make it possible for the individual to alter his attitude rather than choose one of the techniques of resistance. The following are some characteristics of the source: It is one of the variables that is directly connected to the activity of propaganda.

Credibility: Whether in our everyday lives or the findings of our study, we've seen that successful communication coming from a credible source leads in a greater shift of attitude on the part of the target. Credibility was broken down into two components, according to Howland and Weiss. These include a knowledgeable approach and dependability. The aspect of respectability that comes into play here is the question of competence. The word "prestige" refers to a generic characteristic. It all comes down to how much respect the audience has for the propaganda being presented. According to the findings of the study that was conducted with the variable, there is a clear connection between the prestige of the propagandist and the attitude shift that is induced in the listener. nuclear submarines are a distinct possibility. Subjects in one group were informed that the person to speak to was Oppenheimer, a famous physicist, while those in the other group were told that the information was derived from the publication Pravda. Due to the lower regard in which Pravda was held, Oppenheimer was able to deliver his speeches more effectively. that the reason for the difference, based on the Gestalt view, was

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to change the prestige of the source and the meaning of communication in the eyes of the listener to some extent. this was said to be the case because the difference was caused by the Gestalt view. Reliability (purpose): The objective of propaganda is to be able to influence the target audience and to be able to do it reliably. The audience needs to be convinced, and that is the purpose of the impressive communication resource. Example: In one of the studies, there was a recorded discussion about the importance of law enforcement agencies imposing harsher punishments on those who commit crimes. There are two distinct points of origin.

The first person is a convicted felon who has spent his entire life in and out of prison, and the second person is a prosecutor. As a result, making an analogy between the prosecutor and the offender is intended to alter the perspective of the listener since the prosecutor is a knowledgeable and trustworthy authority on legal matters. In addition to being a loved one and a source of enjoyment, being a source of communication is an important factor. Even though the propagandist is attempting to persuade the person, he is content with the effect because he is the liked person and even acts as if he is attempting to persuade him to his way of thinking. Both Mills and Aronson have contributed to research on this topic. Example 1: A stunning and alluring lady began conversing with a group of guys on a subject, and she was successful in swaying their opinions and gaining their respect. Example 2: One strategy for selling a product is to feature well-known people, such as athletes, models, and television personalities, in television commercials. The multi-source effect is a concept that originates from the social influence theory. This concept states that the listener will be more influenced by the message if they hear it from multiple communication sources as opposed to hearing it from just one source. When the message is powerful, the effect is magnified to an even greater degree. One illustration of this would be the fact that having a message come from three different sources rather than just one is more effective. On the other hand, it's possible that a message coming from eleven different sources will have a greater impact than one coming from three.

Characteristics of the Communication: There is a divergence of opinion: The degree to which the opinion of the listener is different from and how effectively the propaganda counters that opinion is another important factor affecting the persuasive power of propaganda. There is no direct link between the magnitude of the difference in attitude change and the magnitude of the attitude shift to remove the inconsistent behavior. If a positive propagandist tries to change an attitude that is either important or unimportant, he will not have the same level of success in

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both instances. For instance, while it is possible for it to alter your outlook and behavior regarding shampoo, it is not possible for it to alter the political view regarding elections. When someone has a strong opinion about anything, they may tend to dismiss any viewpoint that is even somewhat different from their own. Despite this, a different application of propaganda on a topic that is not multi-period might be accepted by the audience. According to Harvey and Sherif's explanation, the current circumstance is an example of an "acceptance area-rejection area." When it comes to strong and extreme attitudes, the space available for the rejection of various forms of propaganda is significantly larger than the space available for its acceptance. When it comes to weak attitudes, the region of acceptance is often far larger than the area of rejection. - Extreme attitudes are ones that are strongly devoted to something.

Communication going in both directions: It is the second essential aspect of the communication process. In one-way communication, just the viewpoint put forth is explained, no counter opinion is offered. The position of the opposing thesis is brought up in communication that goes in both directions, and this opinion is often dismissed. For instance, Ahmet works as a salesperson at a Toyota agency and can explain to consumers about some of the positive aspects of Renault, or occasionally party leaders don't mention other parties at all. When dealing with situations like this, it has been observed that it is more beneficial when there is communication in both directions. Intelligence and education level are two other listener characteristics that interact with one another. In comparison to one-way propaganda, the effectiveness of two-way propaganda will increase in direct proportion to the intelligence and education level of the recipient of the information. It has been shown that one-way propaganda is, under some circumstances, more successful than two-way propaganda. When attempting to solve an issue, showing a person with a low degree of education, intellect, or subject matter understanding two or more potential solutions may cause them to get confused.

The nature of the topic of the propaganda, the reputation of its source, and the different qualities of the audience will decide whether kind of propaganda, one-way or two-way, will be more successful. On the other hand, there are certain circumstances in which two-way propaganda is always more successful. Its purpose is to instill in the audience a sense of defiance and resistance against any counterpropaganda they may come across. When only one side of an argument is presented, the audience is left open to the claims made by the opposing thesis and is more likely to believe the subsequent piece of counterpropaganda. one's attitude, as well as

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to refute the criticism leveled against one's attitude and to defend one's own attitude against criticism in the future. For instance, the most effective strategy to defend one's own perspective against the influence of a political ideology is to vocally oppose and debunk the ideology in question. Emotional-rational communication: Communication that is either wholly emotional or fully intellectual cannot be utilized in any way. The logical and the emotional aspects of a situation are frequently viewed together. The degree to which a person is interested in the topic of communication and how personally relevant it is to that person is an important consideration here. Communication may also be emotional if there is a topic near to the listener, else the sentimentality may be seen unusual by the listener. Example: a politician may become passionate while talking about cost of living or inflation, but it may sound weird when the same is true for Japan. Order in which information is presented in communication: It was believed that at a gathering, what was said by the person who spoke the very last would be remembered the best, making their message more influential on the audience. Because they are more easily recalled, the remarks of the person who spoke last in the meeting tend to have a greater influence on the audience. While the primary studies of persuasion are successful, there are also secondary studies that are successful, as well as results that are mutually supportive. This is even though the research has come to different conclusions regarding whether the message should be conveyed first or last. Again, coming into regular contact with something causes familiarity, but repeatedly hearing a name might give the impression that the person or thing in question is well-known. A listener's comprehension of a message increases with the number of times it is repeated. One excellent illustration of this is seen in advertising.

Attributes of the Object of Desire: when one considers it to be a coincidence and when one thinks of it as propaganda geared at the audience. The degree to which an individual sticks to his or her own attitude is a decisive element in the listener's ability to either reject or embrace propaganda. The degree to which the attitude of the audience differs from that of the propaganda in question is one factor that plays a role in determining how successful the propaganda is. The fact that the audience does not agree with the propaganda, as well as the dominance of the propaganda on the issue, is what defines the kind of propaganda that is used and the impact that it has. Commitment(Engagement): It is the degree to which the listener is willing to commit to his attitude and the degree to which he attaches himself to his attitude. The more deeply ingrained this bond is, the more challenging it will be to adopt a new perspective. An individual

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who has just purchased a new automobile, for instance, is less likely to pay attention to commercials for automobile brands other than the brand of vehicle that they own. Source or tries to alter an inconsequential attitude held by the listener, the circumstance in which the listener is disconnected: Either one will result in a significant shift in mindset. Alternately, the most significant shift in outlook will take place when it contrasts with the listener's point of view. Confidence: People who lack confidence do not place a high value on their own thoughts and ideas, hence it is not difficult for them to alter such ideas and thoughts. One good example of a self-assured individual is Ahmet. On the other hand, Mehmet lacks self-confidence to a significant degree. Many investigations have arrived at the same conclusion, which is that those who have low levels of self-confidence become more persuaded more rapidly. Differences in Intra-Group Dignity The prestige and standing of an individual inside the group determines the extent to which he or she is swayed by the opinions and actions of other members of the group. As an example, the effectiveness of the propaganda will increase in proportion to the reputation of the propaganda. Intellect and Change: Persons who have a high intelligence and education level are less likely to be swayed by propaganda than people who have a poor education level and speak inconsistently and illogically.

The difference between men and women is that women are more open to being influenced by others and are thus easier to convince. An example of this would be the research that he did for Abelson and Lesser, which was a study of high school pupils in the United States. In terms of their receptivity to persuasion, females were shown to be more open than boys; however, this disparity was not found when the same research was carried out on kids in elementary school. This understanding of gender is dependent on the diversity that exists within society as well as the utilization of a range of different methodologies. The need for thinking may be defined as the urge to engage in mentally taxing activities that demand one's full attention. The central approach of persuasion is used on individuals who 85 have a high demand for thinking, whereas the peripheral way of persuasion is used on individuals who have a low need for thinking. Example: The instructor discusses a subject with the class. Challenges the pupils' understanding of the material by asking them challenging questions. And that concludes the session of brainstorming. This is the primary path to take. In addition, it offers stability to the educational system. Even persons who have a strong urge to think might have difficulty focusing on times because of distractions. The listener's weariness and the ambient noise in

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their surroundings are both examples of environmental influences. An example of this strategy would be the use of distraction in political campaigns. Although the person is complimented on the candidate in the message, the individual is distracted by the visual imagery, which prevents them from analyzing the message. People who are prone to self-monitoring are constantly controlling how they come across to others by analyzing social clues. People who are not prone to self-monitoring, on the other hand, do not care what other people think of them and act anyway they choose since they are not concerned with self-monitoring their behavior. According to Sender and DeBono, there are two different methods of persuasion that may be used on those who are prone to self-monitoring and others who are not. Both are types of sales techniques: soft selling and aggressive selling.

Technique for "soft selling" in which the aesthetic qualities of the product are highlighted while the functional aspects of the product are left out of the discussion. It is not concerned with how the product is brought to market but rather with the product's quality and utility instead of how the product is brought to market. A person's age is a factor in whether they can persuade others since, on general, individuals are more influenced by negative information and experiences than by favorable ones. The existence of happy moments in the life of old people may help to account for the fact that they are less susceptible to being impacted by negative circumstances. Featured in the Media: A medium is required for there to be any kind of successful communication - been determined by survey surveys using the technique of sampling In the actual world, it might be challenging to communicate via the mainstream media. Reaching the desired audience is the most significant challenge presented by mass communication.

The flow of information occurs in two stages: first, communication with mass media reaches local opinion leaders directly; after this, opinion leaders share them with their own circle. Even though males are more likely to be involved in politics, women have the potential to be influential opinion leaders in the fashion industry. - The message may be seen by the target, interpreted by the target, and even have its meaning altered to suit the demands of the target. Culture's defining traits are as follows: The process of persuasion and the ability to communicate effectively are both impacted by the qualities of the culture. When compared to collectivist cultures, individualistic cultures place a greater emphasis on the importance of the individual, while collectivist cultures place a greater emphasis on the importance of in-group

harmony and belonging. Differences in how the trustworthiness of the source of information itself is viewed may be attributed to a culture's unique characteristics. Studies in the realm of health that look at the process of persuasion have shown cultural disparities. According to research on persuasion, the effectiveness of a message may be improved by ensuring that both the cultural environment and the chronic culture are in sync with one another. It is not enough for us to examine the components impacting the process of persuasion together if we want to understand how they were convinced or how they resisted being persuaded in the face of propaganda. The degree to which a person will be swayed by a message is determined by the ways in which the factors that influence processes of attitude change interact with one another.

3.The Effect Of Values On Child Psychology

In human existence, a position that should not be overlooked is that of social and moral ideals. Most individuals in educated cultures agree that certain moral and value systems are both accurate and significant. This is what we mean when we talk about values. Within the context of an education in values, it takes place in correct and incorrect ways of thinking. It is essential to place a strong emphasis on the children's education and development while they are still in kindergarten if one wishes to produce adults who are in both good mental and physical health. Because they need to be allowed to freely express their imaginations, ideas, sentiments, and thoughts, because they need to offer self-control, because they need to be attentive to the rights of others, and because they need to have their own cultural values. He acknowledges the assistance that is provided to him in the educational qualities that are shown by youngsters whose values are being educated and accepts it. The youngster has a heightened awareness of his surroundings. Children share stories about times when other people need assistance. Children are keenly aware of those in their environment who need assistance. Children are naturally kind and want to assist people around them. The offer of assistance is communicated verbally as well as via the body language of children. When the youngster has a problem, he will seek for assistance from the people around him. It is the way the youngster expresses gratitude when he is assisted.

The youngster always speaks the truth, even when the circumstance is not ideal. The youngster is responsible for explaining the potential repercussions that may result from

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situations in which he does not behave honestly. The youngster is willing to suffer the repercussions of their dishonest behavior. The youngster maintains control of his feelings. When parents are not around, the youngster demonstrates compliance with the rules. The goals of providing children with an education in values are to cultivate persons who have character, morality, and individuality, as well as to aid such individuals' adaptability to social life. In the context of values education, which refers to the process of transmitting one's moral compass to one's offspring, institutions, and factors such as the family, the school, the environment, the media, and social media all play important roles. The task of teaching children the values of society lies largely within the realm of the educational system. Examining the textbooks that were developed in accordance with the educational program and the curriculum that is followed in children's classes in terms of values education reveals that values education occupies an important area in terms of the process of disclosing the values that already exist.

The youngster is resolute in their goal to complete the activity. When it is appropriate to do so, the youngster puts his desires on hold. The youngster describes events and circumstances that make him feel both excited and anxious. The youngster maintains their composure despite the stressful situation. The child's conduct in unfamiliar settings demonstrates adaptability. It is possible to recognize in the kid behaviors such as refraining from causing physical damage to other people. Opinions and Theories on the Game Educators, instructors, philosophers, and psychologists who consider the game as the primary educational instrument and purpose that should not be kept from the kid have stressed the values of the game and have put up diverse perspectives and put forward different ideas up until this point. Some of the perspectives held by educators, instructors, and philosophers throughout history and up until the present day on the game are as follows: M. Montaigne (1533-1592) stated that there is no such thing as teaching the soul in human beings, that the education of the person should be judged as a whole, and that the training of the body should be the primary focus of education. Space and actual labor, which adults regarded for generations as the sole reason why children were amused and diverted, and as a purposeless profession. Amos Comenius (1592-1671) stated that dramatic plays accompanied by music and rhythm, off education improved the personality formation of children and contributed to moral and value education by keeping the school environment at the same value as play in kindergarten education.

Orff education is a method of early childhood education that emphasizes the importance of play. He linked participation in the game with an individual's need for independence and said that it played a significant part in the process of becoming disciplined and achieving order. "When a youngster is forced to do anything against his will, he does not experience pleasure; rather, he expresses his disgust toward activities that he does not like at all. Nobody is compelled to participate in any games. According to Act and Sevinc (2004), the child's wish to be independent was made clear by the words that he said. F. Frobel (1782-1852) centered his work on the concept of play, which functions as a bridge between two distinct and contradictory themes: natural-spiritual sensation and knowledge. Play operates as a mediator between these two themes. According to Frobel, he mentioned that the game needs to be seen as the ideal spiritual exercise for the person since it has a uniting effect and is like a mechanism. This is something that he said in his book. Because to Frobel's efforts, the idea was thought of as a significant component of kindergarten teaching while the game was being played. According to him, the need to play is an essential one for the person, and the need to play is as vital in the life of a kid as the need to work is in the life of an adult. A youngster can learn whatever they need to know via the medium of play. Because the experience and information gained while playing the game will stick with you forever. He stated that educational and learning toys establish the groundwork for life by helping the person learn by the individual's own efforts, and that this helps the individual prepare for life. According to Frobel, "play consists of the core that determines the existing life of the individual and is the purest and emotionally satisfying occupation of the individual in the kindergarten area." Play is the most emotionally satisfying occupation of the individual in the kindergarten area. Work, not play, is what M. Montessori (1870-1952) considers the activities, values, exercises, games, experiences, and studies that take place in a child's environment. It is the phenomena that occurs when the person in his life is unable to locate a better bargain for the game he plays in his life. The youngster enters an age when he is trying to learn at the same time as he is attempting to better himself via the activity of playing games. During the first six years of a child's life, Maria Montessori referred to it as the "region of sensitivity," and she highlighted that it should be encouraged with play and assessed effectively.

The children like this have the potential to create sophisticated and democratic nations. The youngsters in our care who have just completed the values education course have learned

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how to begin life on an equal footing. They have a lengthy learning life; therefore, they can readily adjust to new circumstances. They are quite proficient in the use of computers, which is natural given that we are living in the era of technology. They are better able to communicate with one another inside the family and with one another as children. They have little trouble adjusting to the academic environment. Our fundamental principles, as well as the information and experience we have of who we are; The capacity to express oneself, particularly in a social setting, is an essential component of self-confidence. It is necessary for the kid or individual to be appreciated and loved, as well as to have adequate belief and capacity in their own abilities, for them to be able to fully express themselves. The level of one's own self-confidence is fluid; it may go up or down at any given moment. It is not constant. It is possible to enhance one's self-confidence because of increased capabilities if they are guided and supported. A person who has a good sense of their own worth would say things like, "I am valuable because I exist," in his perspective. When the significant others in our lives perceive, accept, and approve of us as we are, and when we ourselves feel that we are valuable to other people in our own right, our feeling of self-worth is fostered, supported, and reinforced. It is essential for the kid to experience the importance of his existence that others respect him in all aspects of his life, including his physical existence, his emotions, his behaviors, and his efforts. This includes being attentive to and respectful of the child's feelings. It is necessary for us to have the experience of being useful in the social sense for the feeling of worth to emerge. Each kid is a precious treasure.

The academic success alone may not be sufficient to ensure a person's place in society. Appreciation from others brings a gain in value, whilst criticism brings a loss in value. As adults, we can acknowledge the positive and inspire others to strive for improvement. Let us love and respect our kid or children without conditions whatsoever. Let's give children the impression that they're very being has value, even though they may sometimes act in inappropriate ways. Let's provide them with the chance to hone their talents and expand their skill set so they can better contribute. Provide them with duties that are suitable for their age. Children find entertainment in activities such as watching television and playing computer games. Children might lose track of time and themselves when they are absorbed on an electronic device. They watch action movies while driving about in their fantasy cars competing in races. During this period, a plethora of images that are conjured up by the picture pours over

your youngster. He barely ever can contemplate them. For once, he is unable to respond since he is glued to the television, intent on catching up on anything he may have missed. Make it a point to get your kid away from the screen at least a little bit before it's time for bed. Reduce the amount of time he spends in front of the television and computer so that he is not too tense when it is time for him to go to bed. There need to be a gap of at least one hour between the end of a movie and when one goes to bed. Your youngster will have the ability to interpret what they have learnt if they are given this opportunity. Have a conversation with him about what he's discovered. As a result, you can determine, right away, how the incident is interpreted by him. Explain to him the parts that he doesn't understand and try to put him at rest by telling him that the things that scare him are merely for the purpose of the movie. By doing so, he can free himself of ideas that cause him concern or confusion.

4.How To Teach Values

Because of this, learning the value of tolerance in preschool is extremely essential, and learning the value of empathy has a significant position in terms of maintaining my calm within the context of the social order that is now in place. It is essential for there to be preparations made for this in educational programming, for there to be arrangements made for this in educational programming, and for there to be adaptations made in educational coursework to accommodate values education. It is possible to raise healthy children who are at peace with themselves and their surroundings if education and training programs include a values education component. This helps children to grasp it better and is the way to integrate values education into education and training. It has a good impact on their moral life, and the more consistent, empathic, and physically fit persons are, the higher their welfare level and degree of moral self-actualization are in the community. A person's behavioral patterns about both their surroundings and other people are influenced throughout their whole lives by the socialization process.

The people gain knowledge on how to interact with the people around them, as well as how to behave and the norms that are already in place in society, while playing the game. Instead of learning the word "me," try learning "us." The competition: In addition to this, it is the second most essential emotional nutrient after love in the child's development of social skills

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and linguistic abilities. Children go through a wide range of emotions and get expertise in managing those feelings as they are engaged in gaming activities. During play, children can feel and then express their feelings for the first time. Children are exposed to new situations. Children will argue for their own points of view, they will have pleasure, they will become furious, and they will be astonished. All of this is done by "kids." The involvement of children in meaningful play is a critical component of their education. The kid is aided in recognizing his fundamental interests, wants, and inclinations, as well as in gaining insight into the challenges he faces emotionally. Children can channel their frustration, resentment, and other negative emotions that they are unable to articulate directly into the game. Through the medium of play, he can demonstrate once again the condition of love as well as the manifestation of happiness. Inadvertently, this allows him to share details about his private life with his parents. S. Freud (1920) was the first person to point out that a kid feels his or her emotions via the games that they play. "He saw the relationship between fantasy behaviors and play and said that children experience unconscious desires and difficulties in their games. "Just as we adults talk and rethink our disturbing lives over and over and continue this process until we conclude. "He saw the relationship between fantasy behaviors and play. For a young kid, the first step is to start playing. They play games in which they attempt to get an understanding of their feelings by reliving those feelings. (Özdoğan,2000:115) Offer children chances for growth, education, the acquisition of cognitive abilities, and the development of new habits. The social development of the kid is one of the aspects of growth that should not be disregarded. This is one of the domains. According to Saracho (1998), the importance of play in the individual's overall social development and educational experience cannot be overstated.

The game not only reveals the social behaviors of players but also helps players grow and refine such behaviors. Through play, children can gain experience in a variety of social circumstances, including the capacity to work with one another, the notion of collaboration and sharing, and the ability to discover solutions to the difficulties they face. Individuals who are independent of their field yet loyal to their field may be distinguished from one another by the fact that they have various social accomplishments and experiences, as well as different personal qualities. When the similarities and differences between loyal and independent people in terms of socialization are evaluated, it has been determined that loyal people are more affected by external cognition resources and cues from other people than individuals who are

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independent of their field. Because of this, loyal people are more affected by the phenomenon of sociability, and their levels of sociability are high. Independent people are less likely to be affected by external cognition resources and cues from other people. As a direct consequence of this, the part that play ultimately plays in the process of both social-emotional and cognitive development is significant. Because of the roles he takes on in the game, he is better able to grasp the parts that others play, as well as his own sexual role, and interact with his buddies. By engaging the outside world around him in his games, he learns to perceive events and schemes as if he were living again. He also learns how to be successful in learning the rules of the game, how to be a leader or a team member in the game, and how to win and lose.

The play has a very important place in every moment of life. Play requires the same importance as nutrition, sleep and health are of paramount importance for the child. For this, the game played should be consistent for the cognitive development of children, social emotional development, self-care skills, language development, psycho-motor skills, and all areas of development. Although the play is motivated is an internal activity, it should be in direct proportion between what is presented to the child and his / her wants and needs. So, play is an open-ended activity. It is an activity that can change according to the flow in the time spent with the child. Although play is known as an entertainment and pleasure activity, new information emerges, new emotions are discovered, and it is an enjoyable activity in terms of learning values education. In this study, the effects of Values Education on Values Education of 0-6 Age Group Children were investigated. In the literature reviews, there is no information about the education given by combining values education and playgrounds. The universe of the study was created by using subjective tests according to the scoring method. In the sample of the study, the views of preschool teachers and how kindergarten teachers applied the games and values education combined in the classroom were examined. During my investigation, a Multiple Regression Analysis was carried out to determine how much of an impact the students' educational experiences had on the decisions they made regarding their attitudes, education, and values. This strategy was selected because it is common knowledge that the decision-making processes of instructors and their effectiveness in the game and values education program impact a great deal of wiggle room in terms of the composition of the student body. The decision-making process and the implementation process are the two types of processes that are included in the game and values education curriculum for teachers. the processes of

decision making; It is vital for instructors in schools to have decision making abilities that are applicable to the real-world circumstances, whether those circumstances are favorable or bad. When it comes time to decide, teachers need to pay close attention to the program's current structural state and then make a choice that takes that into account.

5. Giving The Game With Values Education

Schiller (1875) and Spencer (1878) are two prominent figures who advocated for this notion. Play activities, in accordance with this notion, are the dissipation of extra energy via the medium of play as a kind of regulated activities. The youngster feels the need to burn off some of his surplus energy by playing. This theory struggles to provide satisfactory explanations for several situations. The fact that people play games while they are unwell is not a sufficient explanation for why any game may take on unique shapes or why interest might shift from one time to the next. Rest Theory Lazarus (1883) and Patrick (1916), who are the proponents of this theory, stated that the game activity; they argue that it is played with the aim of gaining the energy spent, or to put it another way, closing the energy deficit. This contrasts with the over-consumption of energy, which would be the opposite of the purpose of playing the game. arduous working duration, as well as the fact that the game itself is played to boost one's energy levels—contrary to the hypothesis that extra energy would result. However, ideas are not adequate to explain why children play the games they do.

Preparation for Adult Life Gross (1898) , the founder of this theory, play activity is the emergence of natural skills that can help the individual in his later years and prepare him for life . According to this theory, the game is motivational, and the individual tries the behaviors that he may have in the future as a game. Readiness for life is an inherited trait. Although the individual prepares for his future life through play and learns a lot, this is not a natural motivational preparation. Because the individual does not play games just to learn. Repetition Theory G. Stanley is the creator of this hypothesis. According to Hall (1906), all the movement and balance coordination studies in the game theme are founded on a genetic foundation, and a person will continue to go through the development that he had in his previous life over the course of his life. According to this idea, the individual prepares themselves for work by playing, which involves the abandoning of behaviors that are basic or superfluous on the part

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of the system organism. It is not adequate, according to the currently accepted theory, to explain the inventions and advances that have occurred in children's games since it holds that learned features may be inherited. Instinct Theory Movements and activities that are geared toward the growth and development of instincts are what the currently accepted theory identifies as the essential components of play activity. As there has been less of an emphasis placed on one's intuition, the usefulness of theories within this subject has decreased. The instinct hypothesis cannot adequately describe many different facets of the game.

The Dynamic Game Theories In contrast to the theories in the classical field, game theories in the dynamic field do not study why a kid plays the game; rather, they focus on attempting to comprehend the fundamental elements that constitute the game. Psychoanalytic game theories Freud was the first person to examine mimicked behaviors and imaginative activities while developing his psychoanalytic theory of play activity. This hypothesis was proposed by Freud. In psychoanalytic theory, play is characterized as an activity in which pleasurable experiences are repeated, and in this setup, the child is given the opportunity to regulate the events that take place. According to Freud, the game is not something that happens arbitrarily or by accident; rather, it is the sentiments that people are conscious of or are not aware of. The individual's thoughts and aspirations, which the player has little to no influence over, are reflected in the game. In addition, the game provides the opportunity for the youngster to momentarily disengage from the strain, stress, and conflicts that are caused by the truth, to unwind, and to fortify themselves. The psychoanalytic theorists who came after him saw the game as an important resource forgetting to know the kid and implemented it as an efficient approach for treating the child's mental incompatibilities. Because in the children's game, they may project their sentiments onto other people or things, such as love, hatred, or fury. The excitement, tension, and contradictions that the youngster experiences during the game may lessen because of the child's consistent repeating of these feelings throughout the game. Erikson, on the other hand, interpreted the game not just from a psychoanalytic perspective but also as a physical and cultural reality, in contrast to Freud, who solely looked at it from a psychological one. The Game Theory of Jean Piaget: Piaget, in contrast to most other theories, considered play to be the fundamental component in both the maturation process and cognitive development. Piaget is of the opinion that both assimilation and adaptation are essential for healthy mental growth, and that play is beneficial to healthy mental development.

6. Method Survey Studies

The research is to establish the ways in which preschool children acquire values education via play, a questionnaire study was selected as the preferable form of qualitative research. Qualitative research is a type of research in which qualitative data collection methods such as observation, interviews, and questionnaires are used, and the situations being researched are examined holistically in the natural environment in which they occur. This type of research is known as "grounded theory." In this research, it has been sought to assess the effectiveness of values instruction in youngsters via games connected to current circumstances. It is the resolute approach to putting an end to the unfavorable circumstance. The methodology that I use in my study entails collecting, examining, and interpreting the relevant facts to resolve the issue. My investigation made use of the "Questionnaire Method," which is one of the data gathering strategies described in the primary source. This enabled me to get at the data in an impartial manner and to add my own opinions. To accomplish this goal, first and foremost, the questionnaire approach was used to determine how successful the Values education learning through play program is for children in Turkey in the 0-6 age range. Likert ' scale (Attitude Scale) for the questionnaire questions . In the context of my study, these idioms, and phrases, along with organizations that make use of theoretical notions, were evaluated using a Likert scale with five points. Likert uses this scale to measure people's attitudes. It is articulated in a straightforward manner and takes the shape of a solitary verdict.

The expressions are used to evaluate it. In addition, children in the age range of 0 to 6 years old were asked to verbally state their performance in the process of learning Values Education through play in the questionnaires. These children were also asked to describe the situations in which they frequently encounter theoretical concepts and the situations in which they do not use these concepts. The primary objective of including this circumstance in the survey is to evaluate the effectiveness of children aged 0 to 6 years old in gaining an understanding of Values Education via play, as well as the present standing of the child's potential when they apply theoretical ideas. The research is a supplementary study. When looking at the results of children aged 0 to 6 who are participating in Values Education via play, the results are all produced from the expressions in the five-stage Likert scale. This is done so

that the results may be compared under a single heading. During research on the effectiveness of play-based Values Education 105 instruction for children aged 0 to 6, questions ranging between four and five were posed to the participants.

The primary focus of my investigation is on the establishment in the Turkish province of Izmir that is responsible for carrying out the strategies and plans devised by pre-school educational institutions in that region to teach young children moral and ethical principles through the medium of integrated play education. If this pre-school education establishment is going to be a success with children, its influence on the teaching of children's values must be carefully evaluated, and the program's overall structure needs to be carefully planned. This circumstance is a significant component of the study being conducted. In the course of the investigation, there was a restriction placed on the size of the population that may participate in the questionnaire. The sample group for my research consisted of seventy-five children who are currently enrolled in a pre-school education program at an institution located in Izmir, Turkey. If my research is successful, the scope of the research can be expanded to include other pre-school education institutions located within the province of Izmir, and this will be examined in the sample. The data for the research were gathered via the use of a semi-structured interview form. According to Büyükoztürk et al. (2009), semi-structured interviews include the use of both fixed choice answers and the ability to delve more deeply into the subject matter at hand.

The subject validity of the interview questions was checked by soliciting the feedback of five industry professionals and doing a literature search on the topic at hand before beginning preparations. A preliminary interview was conducted with a teacher, and the responses were documented in writing for the purposes of determining whether the questions were clear and intelligible, as well as whether or not the replies were consistent with the questions that were asked. After that, a knowledgeable person was tasked with reviewing the interviews to determine whether or not the questions that were posed during the interviews were concise, easy to comprehend, and whether or not they adequately addressed the topic that was the focus of the study. It was via this process that we were able to ascertain the internal validity of the question items. According to common knowledge, the concept of "internal validity" in qualitative research refers to the question of whether the researcher can really measure the data he intends to test using the instrument or technique he employs (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2005).

The real practice was begun, face-to-face interviews with the instructors were conducted, and the responses were documented in writing when it was established that the question items were genuine. The researcher came up with the encodings that are included in parenthesis. For instance, F denotes a female instructor whereas E denotes a man teacher. 1Y, 2Y, 3Y, etc. show the amount of professional experience teachers have. The performances of children aged 0 to 6 years old at a Pre-School Education Institution in Izmir, Turkey, in the process of acquiring Values Education via play were included in the sample, and sixty children were chosen for the study based on their capabilities of applying theoretical ideas. Investigation has been done to determine the factors and effects that influence the students' performance in learning theoretical concepts related to Values Education.

The investigation was carried out in great depth using a variety of methods, including inspection, observation, and interviews. Interview request form The following are the interview questions that were sent to the instructors along with the paperwork for the interview:

- 1-When presenting the idea of values in the context of the educational process, what strategies, procedures, resources, and activities do you use?
- 2- Within the framework of values education, which values do you impart onto young people?
- 3- Have you ever attended any classes or training sessions on morals and ethics?
- 4- In what ways might young children benefit from receiving a values education throughout their preschool years?
- 5- When analyzing the activities associated with values education, which of the several possible approaches of assessment do you use?

Since the scale was established for children aged 0 to 6, it was produced in three separate versions (family, teacher, and student) to guarantee that the data is accurate. You are free to use any one of the forms by itself or both together. The form of the scale that was prepared for use 113 with children was done so visually. It is made up of a total of 18 image cards in its whole. Both the family form and the instructor form are Likert scales, each with thirty things to choose from. Both the teacher and family forms had both positive and negative questions and items. There are three different choices available for the produced items, and each one corresponds to

a different frequency at which the behavior is shown. These, the answers are yes, sometimes, and no. The three different versions of the scale—one for the family, one for the instructor, and one for the student—were developed in such a manner as to be able to assess the qualities of respect, responsibility, honesty, collaboration, sharing, and friendship or friendship. Step in the Process of Determining Scale Items Following the completion of a literature review and the identification of the values that can be imparted during preschool, the Preschool Values Scale Teacher and Family Form was created. Included in Awake Balat and Balaban Daal's (2009) list of values that may be taught to young children throughout the preschool years are the principles of respect, responsibility, happiness, collaboration, patience, and honesty. In her book

The Preschool Values Education, Alpoğ (2012) planned activities that were associated with the core values of being able to make the best choice, honesty, love, respect, courage, goodness, responsibility, friendship, and peace. Oztürk Samur (2011) included the following topics in his doctoral thesis, which was titled "the effect of values education program on the social and emotional development of 6-year-old children: group rules, peace, let's get to know ourselves, we are all different, self-confidence, emotions, responsibility, sharing, and cooperation." According to the findings of another piece of research (Dinc, 2011), children can learn important life lessons such as self-respect, selfcontrol, responsibility, cooperation, love, respect, honesty, and patience during their time in preschool. After completing the examination of the relevant literature, open-ended questions on the core values of respect, responsibility, honesty, collaboration, sharing, and friendship/friendship in the workplace were administered. In addition, the items were chosen by soliciting the feedback of five professionals in the area who are currently employed at various educational institutions. It has been attempted to guarantee that the items on the scale contain wording that is easy to comprehend and that they are in conformity with the norms of grammar by having language professionals review them. Because of the adjustments made by the language specialist, the teacher and family form now consist of thirty different components. Draft items were written one after the other, and it's true that there weren't always any alternatives placed in front of them at times.

The questionnaire has been divided into two primary sections for your convenience. Questions pertaining to theoretical concepts and evaluative judgments are asked in the first section of the exam. In this setting, the game consists of statements on MEB Programs and the Agency, as well as questions broken up into five sections. To evaluate the level of success

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achieved by businesses, a 5-stage model is used. Likert The Attitude Scale was used in its development (Attitude Scale). They have decided at what stage they are inclined to the 20 questions posed to the consumers in the survey. These statements include the judgements of "strongly disagree," "disagree," "partially agree," "agree," and "strongly agree," and they are requested to offer replies based on these judgments.

These evaluations are rated, and this is how they break down:

1. I strongly disagree, 2. I do not agree, 3. I only partly agree, 4. I do agree, and, 5. I strongly agree by incorporating teachings on morality and ethics into classroom games, the research consisted of 20 inquiries, each of which adhered to one of four primary scenarios. In the first section of the questionnaire, which focuses on children, the questions asked center on four primary aspects, which are detailed further down. The following are some expressions concerning the first variable, the game, which are based on values education: 1. In the absence of access to information about the necessary knowledge, combining the teaching of values with the opportunity to play is an important factor. 2. The circumstances that are required to teach the morals and ethics that should be acquired via play should be made available. 3. the employment of books that force the slope of values and games onto their readers. 4. When conducting activities for values education using the game, the level of preparedness of the pupils is considered. In the second section of the questionnaire, there were four questions added with the purpose of determining how efficient and successful the decision-making element was on the performance of both the instructors and the students. These phrases are listed in their respective order below: I will never give up on making choices, even if my studies in values education don't allow me to attain the objective with the 1.game. 2. Whenever I am faced with a challenge in values education studies involving a game, I do not hesitate to put my decisions into action. When making decisions, I always make sure to think about what my students want since I think it will help me make better choices. 4. If the judgments I make have a negative impact on the path, I will undoubtedly take the appropriate precautions.

The third section of the questionnaire is comprised of four question sentences, the purpose of which is to determine the level of effectiveness and efficiency exhibited by the practice behavior of the teachers who responded to the questions asked in the questionnaire. These phrases are listed in their respective order below: 1. I believe that the actions I have taken

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are sufficient to eradicate the unfavorable circumstances I have encountered because of putting the decisions I have made into action, and I am requesting assistance from the School Manager or the Guidance and Psychological Counseling Unit. 2. Even if I find myself in a challenging circumstance because of the unfavorable reactions I have encountered as a consequence of the choices I have made, I do not feel that my efforts to control the classroom will produce favorable outcomes. I don't know how successful the school principal is in the negative feedback I get about the judgments I make, so I listen to the authorities and attempt to find a solution to the issue in the same way that I would in any other situation. 4. Even though I am a victim of the negativity I received at school when I make and execute choices, I do not think that my efforts will generate outcomes when I conduct the activity because I do not believe that my efforts will produce results. There are three questions in the fourth section of the questionnaire that are designed to assess how successful and efficient the practice behavior of the instructors was.

These teachers were the ones that answered the questions asked in the questionnaire. These phrases are listed in their respective order below: 1. Whenever I am having trouble putting the judgments we made based on the kids' performances into action, I discuss the problem with my principal. 2. If the students are dissatisfied with the way in which the choices, I make in accordance with the requirements of the students are implemented, I direct them to the Guidance and Psychological Counseling Unit so that they may seek further assistance there. 3. I functionalize the game and values education by splitting the kids into age-appropriate groups to guarantee that the students will be happy with the experience. There are three questions in the fifth section of the questionnaire that are designed to assess how successful and efficient the practice behavior of the instructors was. These teachers were the ones that answered the questions asked in the questionnaire. These phrases are listed in their respective order below: 1. One of the most significant aspects of capturing the attention of a kid is to combine the teaching of morals and ethics with fun activities. 2. It is feasible to raise the potential of pupils by combining the idea of values education with the medium of games. 3. The idea that children can learn important life lessons through play adds a fresh facet to the educational experience; as a result, the idea that children can learn important life lessons through play is gaining popularity.

7. Conclusion

The application of values education studies in Turkey is based on an international study that was initially prepared for the 50th Anniversary celebrations of the United Nations in 1995 under the name of "Living Values Education Program (YDEP)" supported by UNESCO. This study was used as the foundation for the implementation of values education studies in Turkey. Along with other universal values, such as the child's sense of democracy, sense of justice and freedom, as well as the sense of justice and friendship included in the program of the Ministry of National Education, this project has been extensively used in schools, books, puppets, events, children's films, and animations, and finally children's games. UNESCO has been a major supporter of this initiative, which has been used in a wide variety of settings, including schools, books, puppets, and events. It is hoped that this would result in the acquisition of fundamental values such as a sense of honesty, a feeling of self-control, a sense of patience, a sense of respect, a sense of love, a sense of responsibility, patriotism, and compassion. Play, which is at the beginning of most of the individual's most frequent acts, gives the kid the opportunity to learn universal values without the child being aware that this is happening. Simply because the kid is a social value whose primary objective is to have a good time.

The capability gained in this way is essential for the child to be able to make his own decisions with his own free will and to be able to take responsibility for his decisions without being dependent on anyone else (Dirican and Dal, 2014: 45). This ability is important for the child to be able to make his own decisions with his own free will and to be able to make his own decisions with his own free will. The healthy spiritual development of individuals is greatly aided by the participation in various games. One of the most useful approaches to a child's education is the utilization of play activities. Play is also the foundation upon which creative theater classes are built, the significance of which has only relatively lately been acknowledged by social theorists and educational scientists. Every setting in which the game is played fosters the development of admirable characteristics, including cheerfulness, friendliness, compassion, candor, and tolerance. Because being joyful is a prerequisite for practicing the qualities that already exist. People have a significant amount of fun participating in gaming activities.

The children's enjoyment of playing games of all kinds requires them to have access to a wide variety of games, including traditional games. traditional game: These are activities that

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represent the values, culture, traditions, and customs of the community in which people live (Bozkurt and Sozer, 2018: 304). When playing games, children should be active. The individual should be aware of the guidelines for the game, devise a game plan, confidently represent his team, be able to gauge the amount of attention he is giving to the activity, enjoy himself while playing, recognize when he is making a mistake, and be held accountable for his error within the parameters of the guidelines for the classroom. In the process of instilling moral principles in children, it is important to establish settings in which children may acquire these principles via doing and experiencing rather than listening to adult's lecture, and it is also essential that children be given the chance to engage in play. The youngster who plays traditional games at home or at school can learn while having fun while playing. Traditional games may be played either at home or at school. This is how learning sticks with a person forever.

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